

29 **Abstract**

30 A hallmark of Alzheimer's disease (AD) is the extracellular aggregation of toxic amyloid-beta
31 (A β) peptides in form of plaques. Here, we identify netoglitazone, an antidiabetic compound
32 previously tested in humans, as an A β aggregation antagonist. Netoglitazone improved
33 cognition and reduced microglia activity in a mouse model of AD. Using quantitative whole-
34 brain three-dimensional histology (Q3D), we precisely identified brain regions where
35 netoglitazone reduced the number and size of A β plaques. We demonstrate the utility of Q3D
36 in preclinical drug evaluation for AD by providing a high-resolution brain-wide view of drug
37 efficacy. Applying Q3D has the potential to improve pre-clinical drug evaluation by providing
38 information that can help identify mechanisms leading to brain region-specific drug efficacy.

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40 **Significance statement**

41 Alzheimer's disease (AD) is the most prevalent neurodegenerative disease. Its primary
42 symptom is progressive cognitive decline, which impairs executive brain functions and
43 deprives patients of their autonomy in life. Experimental and clinical evidence points to the
44 critical pathophysiological role of the amyloid-beta (A β) peptide. Despite some limited
45 successes in AD immunotherapy targeting A β , AD is still incurable. Here, we use an innovative
46 pipeline for accurate whole-brain measurements of A β load to test the efficacy of the
47 antidiabetic compound, netoglitazone. We found that netoglitazone decreases A β burden in
48 certain brain areas but not in others. Region-specific assessment of anti-A β efficacy may be
49 useful in the development of effective drugs against Alzheimer's disease.

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51 **Keywords:** Alzheimer's disease; amyloid beta aggregates; amyloid plaques; peroxisome
52 proliferators activated receptor-gamma; netoglitazone; microglia; neuroinflammation.

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56 Introduction

57 Alzheimer's disease (AD) is a prevalent neurodegenerative disease which causes an
58 inexorable decline in cognitive abilities, affecting the life of patients and of their caregivers and
59 eventually leading to dementia and death [1]. Given that the strongest risk factor for AD is age,
60 and considering that life expectancy is increasing in most parts of the world, it is anticipated
61 that the incidence of AD will increase.

62 In AD, the amyloidogenic peptide amyloid beta ($A\beta$) is liberated from its precursor protein APP
63 and aggregates into fibrils, giving rise to structures termed "neuritic plaques" by Alois
64 Alzheimer. These aggregated species serve as templates and seeds for the nucleation of
65 further $A\beta$ [2-4] aggregation. According to the amyloid cascade hypothesis [5], $A\beta$ aggregation
66 is the primary cause of AD which induces all downstream aspects of neurodegeneration
67 (aggregation of Tau protein, astrocyte and microglia activation, and eventually neuronal loss).

68 While familial forms of AD are often caused by $A\beta$ overexpression, there is a continuing debate
69 about the importance of $A\beta$ in sporadic AD [6]. Many studies have shown that total $A\beta$
70 deposition in humans correlate poorly with cognitive decline [7], and intellectually healthy
71 individuals can carry remarkable $A\beta$ loads in their brains. Moreover, therapeutic trials with the
72 anti- $A\beta$ antibodies, crenezumab, aducanumab, solanezumab, lecanemab, and gantenerumab
73 have delivered marginal results despite well-documented efficacious pharmacodynamics and
74 impressive removal of brain $A\beta$. [8-10]. In addition, severe side effects have been reported,
75 including brain edema and bleeding [11, 12]. Coupled with the long-term treatment duration
76 and the significant costs associated with therapy, it is crucial to gain a deeper understanding
77 of the disease mechanisms and explore more effective treatment strategies.

78 While none of the clinical trials with anti- $A\beta$ antibodies have yet delivered substantial
79 therapeutic results, it is interesting to note that some antibodies had no discernible effect on
80 the course of the disease whereas others appear to yield statistically meaningful, though very
81 limited, beneficial effects[13-16]. The failure rate of AD clinical trials may be attributed to
82 multiple reasons. Each of these antibodies target different epitopes and even different
83 aggregational states and conformers of $A\beta$, and such parameters are likely to influence their
84 therapeutic efficacy. However, the expression of APP and of the components responsible for
85 its catabolic conversion into $A\beta$ (e.g. BACE-1, presenilins, nicastrin, and several other
86 proteins) is known to vary by anatomical brain region [16-20]. This would result in distinct
87 region-specific drug efficacies. In addition, many of the brain functions affected by AD are
88 related to specific brain regions, not necessarily overlapping with the regiospecificity of AD-
89 drugs [21, 22]. However, the available data on the regional distribution of $A\beta$ in the brain are
90 limited, mostly due to lack of suitable technology. Amyloid load can be measured in clinical

91 and preclinical studies using various techniques, including PET imaging, stereometric
92 immunohistochemistry, ELISA, and western blotting [23-27]. However, these approaches
93 either lack scalability to sample the entire brain (histology) or have no or very low spatial
94 resolution (ELISA, PET). Taking into account the highly compartmentalized structure of the
95 brain and region specific functions and symptoms, selective vulnerability, and
96 pharmacodynamics [28], the testing of AD drugs requires imaging tools that are highly
97 sensitive and can afford high spatial resolution.

98 Investigation of cheaper and less invasive therapies, such as lifestyle interventions, non-drug
99 interventions, and repurposed drugs, may provide alternative approaches that can
100 complement or replace current treatments for AD [29]. In addition, repurposing existing drugs
101 already approved for other diseases may provide a more efficient and cost-effective approach
102 to developing new treatments for AD [30]. The present work builds on a previous study that
103 screened compounds to target A β aggregation in vitro and identified netoglitazone, an FDA-
104 approved thiazolidinedione (TZD) family antidiabetic compound, as an A β modifier from *in*
105 *vitro* [31]. Here, we present a standardized procedure for screening anti-amyloid compounds
106 in vivo. Our pipeline includes high-resolution 3D pharmacodynamic analysis, RNA
107 sequencing, and behavioral assays to test molecules at the brain level. The in vivo tests show
108 that netoglitazone reduces A β load and microglia activity in a region-specific manner, and
109 improves cognition in Alzheimer's mouse models. Our approach is generalizable and
110 applicable to any anti-A β compound.

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123 **Results**

124 *Long-term treatment with netoglitzazone significantly reduces cognitive deficits in APP/PS1* 125 *mice*

126 Previous findings showed that netoglitzazone decreases the aggregation of A β fibrils in cell-
127 free in vitro and in vivo models of *C. elegans*, as well as penetrates the blood-brain barrier of
128 mice when administered orally [31]. Thus, we investigated the removal of neuritic plaques by
129 netoglitzazone in APPPS1 mice [32]. We administered netoglitzazone orally at a low (25mg/ml)
130 or high (75mg/ml) dose, beginning at the age of two months and continuing for 90 or 180 days,
131 referred to as "short-term treatment" and "long-term treatment", respectively (Figure 1A).
132 During the long-term treatment, blood samples were taken at 7 and 28 days after initiating the
133 treatment, and drug levels were quantified (Figure 1A). The measured drug concentrations in
134 plasma were 6297 ng/ml and 6272 ng/ml (SD = 6736) at 7 and 28 days, respectively, after
135 starting the low dose treatment. For the high dose treatment, the measured drug
136 concentrations in plasma were 21834 ng/ml and 13544 ng/ml (SD = 2364) at 7 and 28 days,
137 respectively, after starting the treatment. These findings indicate that the drug attains stable
138 plasma levels over the course of a month (Figure 1B). We then investigated whether high
139 doses of netoglitzazone could improve behavioral outcomes in APPPS1 mice [32]. The
140 behavioral response of mice was examined using a range of paradigms and the outcomes
141 were contrasted with those observed in untreated APPPS1 mice. To control for non-specific
142 effects, wild-type (WT) littermate mice were also tested after receiving either a high dose of
143 netoglitzazone or phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) orally. All behavioral tests were conducted
144 when the mice were approximately 8 months old, shortly before receiving their final daily oral
145 administration of the drug. The results showed that netoglitzazone treatment led to significant
146 improvements in contextual fear memory, innate anxiety-like behaviors, and temporal order
147 memory, compared to non-treated mice (Figure 1C,D,E). However, no improvements were
148 observed in basal locomotor activity or spatial recognition memory (Supplementary Figure 1).

149 The anxiety-like behaviors of APPPS1 and WT mice were evaluated by conducting the
150 light/dark box paradigm. Treated APPPS1 mice showed an increased distance moved in the
151 light compartment as compared to untreated animals. These results indicate that
152 netoglitzazone has anxiolytic effects in APPPS1 animals while not affecting their general maze
153 exploration (Figure 1C).

154 To assess the effect of netoglitzazone on contextual fear memory, the freezing behavior during
155 training and testing was analyzed as previously described [33]. The percentage of time spent
156 displaying freezing behavior was calculated for each condition and time-point (24h and 48h
157 after conditioning). Results showed that after 24 hours, netoglitzazone-treated mice displayed

158 significantly more freezing behavior compared to the PBS-treated mice, regardless of
159 genotype. 48 hours after conditioning, both APPPS1 and WT mice treated with netoglitazone
160 exhibited increased freezing time compared to their respective PBS-treated controls,
161 indicating a potential deficit in fear memory in untreated animals (Figure 1D).

162 To assess the potential effect of netoglitazone on temporal memory, the temporal order
163 memory test was conducted on both APPPS1 and WT mice. The results showed that APPPS1
164 mice exhibited impaired temporal order memory, whereas no such impairment was observed
165 in WT mice. However, the impairment in temporal order memory observed in the
166 netoglitazone-treated APPPS1 group was restored to control levels (Figure 1E).

167 These findings provide evidence for the efficacy of netoglitazone in improving the temporal
168 short-term memory of APPPS1 mice.

169 Furthermore, we assessed the spatial memory abilities of the animals using the Y-maze
170 paradigm. We observed no significant differences in the time spent in the novel arm among
171 the different treatments and genotypes, indicating that netoglitazone treatment did not improve
172 short-term spatial memory (Supplementary Figure. 1A, 1B). We further evaluated the effect
173 of netoglitazone on basal locomotor activity by subjecting APPPS1 and WT mice to the open
174 field paradigm. Our findings indicate that netoglitazone treatment led to a trend towards a
175 decrease in basal locomotor activity in WT mice, as evidenced by a reduction in the distance
176 travelled compared to PBS-treated WT mice. However, there was no effect on basal locomotor
177 activity in APPPS1 mice, as both treated and control mice showed a similar total distance
178 moved (Supplementary Figure 1C).

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180 *Voxel-based statistics of whole-brain drug efficacy shows regional and dose-dependent*
181 *effectiveness of netoglitazone in decreasing A β aggregates*

182 To assess the effects of netoglitazone on the amyloid burden in the brain, two groups of 2-
183 month old APPPS1 mice (30 mice/group) were treated daily for a short-term (90 days) or long-
184 term (180 days) period with 100-300 μ L of either a low dose (25 mg/ml day/mouse) or a high
185 dose of netoglitazone (75 mg/ml day/mouse) by oral administration, after which they were
186 sacrificed. PBS was administered to control mice. All brains were extracted and subjected to
187 focused electrophoretic tissue clearing (FEC) [34], A β staining, and whole-brain imaging
188 (Supplementary Figure 2A). The brains were rendered transparent and luminescent
189 conjugated polythiophenes (LCPs) [35] were used to label the amyloid plaques. These
190 plaques were then imaged across the whole brain with a light sheet fluorescence microscope
191 [36]. Plaques were automatically segmented and regionally quantified using previously
192 described methods [34]. The average plaque count and plaque size within 25- μ m voxels were

193 determined for each treatment cohort and presented in a heatmap to show the difference in
194 number and size of plaques between multiple brain areas and treatment conditions
195 (Supplementary Figure 3A-B). To intuitively visualize the therapeutic effect of the two dosages
196 of netoglitazone in the two cohorts, we compared 25- μm voxels corresponding to the average
197 number or plaque size between cohorts (short-term or long-term treatment) and dosages by
198 inferential statistics [34] and depicted them for the whole brain. Voxels revealing a decrease
199 or increase in plaque count and size were highlighted with two different scale bars. This
200 allowed us to identify voxels significantly altered by the action of netoglitazone and to generate
201 digitally resliced p-value heatmaps ($p < 0.05$) in coronal sections. (Figure 2, Figure 3 and
202 Supplementary Videos). We also investigated the differences in plaque count and mean size
203 between treatment groups in 52 neuroanatomical regions defined by the Allen Brain Atlas [37]
204 (Figure 2, Figure 3 and Supplementary File 1). In the low-dose cohorts, heatmaps of p-values
205 at voxel level showed that the effect of short-term treatment with netoglitazone promoted a
206 decrease in the count of plaques in certain areas belonging primarily to the olfactory, striatal,
207 and thalamic areas compared to PBS-treated mice (Figure 2**Figure 2A**), while long-term
208 treatment reduced the count of plaques in areas belonging primarily to the olfactory, hindbrain,
209 and visual areas (Figure 2B). However, the low dose long-term treatment also induced a
210 scattered increase in the hippocampal, cortical, striatal, and midbrain areas.

211 With regard to the high-dose short-term treatment cohort, the drug's effect in reducing the
212 count of plaques was observed extensively in the hindbrain, midbrain, striatum, and olfactory
213 areas (Figure 2C). In a similar pattern, a decrease in the count of plaques following long-term
214 high-dose treatment was observed in certain areas of the olfactory, striatum, pallidum,
215 hindbrain, and midbrain regions (Figure 2D). In addition, we studied the effect of the drug on
216 mean plaque size. Using voxel-p-value maps, we observed that a short-term treatment with
217 low-dose netoglitazone resulted in a strong and widespread decrease in plaque size in
218 olfactory, hippocampal, striatal, thalamic, and midbrain areas (Figure 3A). When the low dose
219 of drug was administered for long-term, an increase in plaque size was mainly detected in
220 optical cortex, visual area, hippocampus, striatum, and hindbrain. (Figure 3B). When we
221 administered a high dose of netoglitazone for short-term, we observed a significant decrease
222 in plaque size in hippocampus, striatum, thalamus, hypothalamus, midbrain, and hindbrain,
223 but we also observed a diffuse increase in olfactory, hippocampal, cortical, and striatal areas
224 (Figure 3C). Examining long-term high-dose treatment, we observed a significant decrease in
225 plaque size in orbital cortex, olfactory area, hippocampus, thalamus, hypothalamus, midbrain,
226 and hindbrain regions (Figure 3D). In all the cases described above, we have noticed a parallel
227 distribution of effects in the two hemispheres.

228 In summary, when given at a high dose over extended periods, netoglitazone was highly
229 effective in reducing both the number and average size of plaques. Conversely, the low dose
230 of netoglitazone showed greater efficacy in reducing plaque count and size when administered
231 for shorter durations. Nevertheless, there were instances where plaque average size
232 increased unfavorably (Supplementary Figure 3C).

233 We further validated our 3D histology results with 2D immunohistochemistry (IHC) and
234 immunofluorescence microscopy (IF). A group of 2-month old APPPS1 mice (30 mice) were
235 treated daily for 180 days with either a low-dose (25mg/ml day/mouse) or a high-dose of
236 netoglitazone (75mg/ml day/mouse) by oral administration. Control treatments included oral
237 administration of PBS. Mice were sacrificed 180 days after the start of the treatment. Brains
238 were split in two hemispheres. 18 slides of 6 μm each (6 slides per treatment dosage/control)
239 were cut from each hemisphere and subjected to A β staining with an anti-A β antibody. 3
240 slides/condition were stained for both IHC and IF and imaged with either a Zeiss Axiophot light
241 microscope or a Leica SP5 confocal microscope (Supplementary Figure 4A). Whole sagittal
242 slices (for IHC) or smaller selected areas of cortex, hippocampus and thalamus (for IF) were
243 analyzed, and the number of pixels covered by plaques were counted with ILASTIK [38]
244 (Supplementary Figure 4B) to evaluate the efficacy of the drug in reducing plaque count using
245 quantitative 2D analysis did not yield any significant differences between the treated and
246 control groups of mice. Consequently, we were unable to demonstrate any substantial effect
247 of the drug in reducing the number of plaques in the brain tissue using 2D histology. While this
248 method is a useful tool for evaluating changes in plaque morphology and distribution, it may
249 not be sensitive enough to detect subtle differences in plaque count between the groups.

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251 *Netoglitazone decreases microglia activation in a dose-dependent manner*

252 To test the effect of netoglitazone on neuroinflammation and gliosis, 3 mice per group (3 high-
253 dose, 3 low-dose, 3 PBS-treated mice) were treated daily for 180 days with either a low-dose
254 (25mg/ml day/mouse) or a high-dose of netoglitazone (75mg/ml day/mouse) by oral
255 administration. Control treatments included oral administration of PBS. Mice were sacrificed
256 180 days after the start of the treatment, their brains were extracted, and the hemispheres
257 were separated by a sagittal cut. The right hemispheres were subjected to a modified version
258 of DISCO clearing [39] and stained for microglia with Iba1 antibody. For imaging, a 640nm
259 laser and a F76 647SG long pass filter were used. Transparent whole hemispheres were
260 imaged at $3.26 \times 3.26 \times 3 \mu\text{m}^3$ (X \times Y \times Z) voxel size resolution. Raw microscopy images
261 (Supplementary Figure 3) were transformed and registered to the coordinate space of the
262 Allen Brain Atlas [40] with cubic-voxel side-resolution of 25 μm . We performed automated

263 microglia segmentation and regional density quantification using a customized computational
264 pipeline aimed at high-speed processing of half-brain mouse datasets. The pipeline consists
265 of three main steps: (i) image restoration aimed at reducing intensity undulations of the
266 background and increasing signal to noise ratio [95], (ii) microglia segmentation in 3D using
267 intensity-based pixel classification, and (iii) regional microglia-density quantification.
268 Techniques such as parallel programming for shared memory architectures (OpenMP) and
269 memory mapping are employed to reduce the processing time. More details for the pipeline
270 can be found in the Methods section and the corresponding github repository. After
271 segmentation, we generated 3D maps of statistically affected voxels by computing a voxel-
272 wise p-value, between each of the treated cohorts and the PBS-treated cohort. We measured
273 the total volume covered by microglia in each hemisphere of the three different cohorts, and
274 observed a significant reduction in Iba1⁺ microglia in mice treated with the high dose of the
275 drug (1.98 mm³) compared to those treated with PBS (4.15 mm³). Surprisingly, mice treated
276 with the low dose of the drug showed an increase in Iba1⁺ microglia in the brain stem,
277 hypothalamus and thalamus regions compared to PBS (Figure 4A). Next, we analyzed the
278 correlation between the decrease and increase in plaque density and microglia volume in mice
279 that received long-term treatment. On this end, we performed a spatial colocalization of the
280 statistically significant voxel maps for microglia and plaques, and computed the number of
281 voxels that displayed a statistically significant effect (increase or decrease) in both microglia
282 and plaque maps. There was a high correlation between the decrease of plaques and
283 decrease of microglia in mice treated with a high drug dose, while in mice treated with a low
284 dose the decrease in microglia was highly correlated with the increase in plaques (Figure 4B).

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286 *Netoglitazone alters gene expression in a dose-dependent manner*

287 To investigate the gene expression changes promoted by the different netoglitazone
288 treatments, we verified the genetic changes following the two different dosages of
289 netoglitazone after long-term treatment. 17 mice (7 high-dose, 3 low-dose, 7 PBS-treated
290 mice) were treated for 180 days. The hemispheres of these mice were separated, and one
291 hemisphere per sample was analyzed for the differentially expressed genes (DEGs) by RNA
292 sequencing (RNA-Seq). Treatment with low-dose netoglitazone promoted a significant change
293 in expression of 361 DEGs compared to the PBS-treated mice. 135 genes were upregulated,
294 whereas 226 genes were downregulated (Supplementary Files 2-5). Among the top 20 most
295 significantly upregulated DEGs, we found several members of the immediate early gene (IEG)
296 family, including Fos, Arc, Erg4, Fosb, Fosl2, Apold1, Junb, Dusp1, Ier2, Egr3, Nptx2 and Btg2
297 (Figure 5 and Supplementary Files 3,5). By contrast, the most significantly downregulated
298 genes seemed to be involved in several independent processes, with the most relevant in

299 regulation of circadian rhythm (DBP), collagen production (Col6a1), modulation of neuronal
300 toxicity (Wsb1), and drug metabolism (Fmo2). The number of DEGs whose expression was
301 significantly altered following high-dose netoglitazone administration, compared with control,
302 was very low. The significantly increased genes turned out to be only five (CD68, Gpnmb,
303 Serpina3n, Cd180, Ccl3), mainly related to inflammatory mechanisms and immune response,
304 while the decreased gene was only one (Gm26917). (Figure 5 and Supplementary Files 2,4).

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328 Discussion

329 There is increasing evidence that complete, rapid amyloid clearance could be key to
330 attenuating the progression of AD [41]. Therefore, identifying drugs that effectively disrupt A β
331 aggregation could be a valuable strategy to combat AD. PPAR γ receptor activation can
332 counteract the pro-inflammatory and pro-oxidant environment in the CNS, central to AD
333 pathogenesis, making them an attractive pharmacological target [42-48]. Pre-clinical and
334 clinical studies have shown that TZDs, a group of PPAR γ agonists, can reduce A β generation
335 and release, improve learning and memory, and decrease amyloid pathology in a time- and
336 dose-dependent manner [49-53]. However, the therapeutic efficacy of these molecules in
337 clinical trials was found to be modest, possibly due to imprecise assessments of their impact
338 on A β plaque load [54-58]. More comprehensive methods may be required to evaluate the
339 effectiveness of these drugs.

340 Here, we aimed to evaluate the efficacy of the experimental anti-diabetic drug netoglitazone,
341 a PPAR γ agonist belonging to the TZD group, in treating, preventing or inhibiting the formation,
342 deposition, accumulation or persistence of amyloid aggregates in vivo [59]. To overcome the
343 limitations of previous studies, we used three-dimensional histology and computational
344 methods to holistically evaluate the efficacy of netoglitazone and to uncover differences at the
345 regional anatomical level. Netoglitazone has shown promise in previous drug-repurposing
346 strategies and in vitro assays by decreasing fibril mass concentration in a dose-dependent
347 manner and improving the fitness of AD worm models (*C. elegans*) by reducing the number of
348 aggregates that are formed [31]. These results suggest that netoglitazone may have anti-
349 amyloid properties and be effective in treating AD, which motivated us to further investigate
350 its efficacy in vivo.

351 We studied the effects of netoglitazone in an animal model of AD and found that a high dose
352 can improve fear and temporal memory in APPPS1 mice. Using Q3D analysis [60], we
353 discovered that the impact of the drug on plaques depended on the dosage and administration
354 period, leading to both decreased and increased plaques in various brain regions. Our study
355 found that higher doses of the drug had a greater and more optimal impact in reducing plaque
356 number at long-term treatment, while lower doses were better at reducing both plaque number
357 and size in short-term treatment. Additionally, we found that the boundaries of drug action did
358 not always correspond to historically defined neuroanatomical areas, suggesting the existence
359 of hitherto unrecognized local modifiers within the brain of hosts. Through Q3D, we were able
360 to identify both favorable and unfavorable changes in amyloid quantity that could not have
361 been detected with traditional biochemistry or histology techniques.

362 Our research suggests that the varying effects of netoglitazone, contingent on the dose and
363 duration of administration, may be linked to the distinctive expression levels of PPAR γ
364 receptors in the brain, different cell types, and the specific stage of the disease [61]. To gain
365 insights into this phenomenon, we examined pioglitazone, a drug similar to netoglitazone,
366 which has been found to exert control over PPAR γ receptor target genes in neural cells in a
367 dose-dependent and cell-specific manner. The study of pioglitazone sheds light on the
368 underlying mechanisms that determine the beneficial or adverse effects of netoglitazone,
369 varying according to the dosage used and the specific cell types involved [61].

370 An additional factor that may contribute to the varying effects of netoglitazone is the disparity
371 in PPAR γ receptor expression between males and females [61] Our study did not differentiate
372 between male and female groups. Furthermore, the present study is limited by the spatial
373 resolution of our Q3D mesoSPIM equipment which does not allow for discriminating structures
374 smaller than 3 μ m isotropic. For this reason, Q3D could be optimally combined with orthogonal
375 techniques such as single-cell sequencing and spatial transcriptomics, thereby providing a
376 comprehensive and precise descriptions of spatial drug responses .

377 Our 3D histology study revealed that the efficacy of netoglitazone in reducing amyloidosis
378 exhibits spatial-temporal specificity. This intriguing finding suggests that the drug's
379 effectiveness in combating amyloid plaques might vary based on the location within the brain
380 and the stage of disease progression. The implications of these observations extend beyond
381 netoglitazone and may have generalizable implications for anti-amyloid therapies.

382 In summary, our study highlights the intricate relationship between netoglitazone's effects and
383 dosage, administration duration, cell type, disease stage, and potentially even gender
384 differences in PPAR γ receptor expression. Understanding these multifaceted factors can
385 contribute to optimizing therapeutic approaches and uncovering novel treatment strategies for
386 amyloid-related disorders and possibly other neurodegenerative diseases.

387 Inflammation and gliosis are histological hallmarks of AD and can be observed in APPPS1
388 mice from an early age on [62]. A β plaque-associated reactive microgliosis is seen in rodent
389 models of AD and human cases, indicating that A β deposition leads to microglial activation
390 [63-66]. PPAR γ agonists have been shown to inhibit microglial activation and inflammation,
391 making them a potential therapeutic option for AD [67-69]. Q3D allows for precisely quantifying
392 the changes in microglia volume following long-term treatment with netoglitazone. We found
393 that high-dose netoglitazone significantly reduced the total volume of microglia throughout the
394 brain, particularly in the cortex, and this correlated with a decrease in A β plaques. In contrast,
395 low-dose netoglitazone had a mixed effect on microglia in a spatially-dependent manner.

396 These findings suggest that a long-term high dose of netoglitzone may reduce inflammation
397 and enhance the phagocytic activity of microglia, which facilitates the removal of A β deposits.

398 We measured gene expression changes in APPPS1 mice treated with different doses of
399 netoglitzone and compared them to PBS. Among the genes that showed a significant
400 difference between low-dose netoglitzone and PBS, the 20 most upregulated genes were
401 immediate early genes (IEGs) associated with neuronal plasticity and memory formation [70].
402 This suggests that low-dose treatment stimulated a stress and inflammation response,
403 potentially due to the drug's localized efficacy throughout the brain [71-75]. On the other hand,
404 high-dose treatment led to a small number of differentially expressed genes, mostly related to
405 microglia activation and immune defense mechanisms, indicating a decrease in amyloidosis
406 and inflammation throughout the brain [76-81]. These findings are consistent with our
407 observations from the whole-brain maps.

408 Beyond its significance in the evaluation of netoglitzone in AD, the present study showcases
409 Q3D as an advanced technique capable of identifying phenomena that had gone undetected
410 by conventional microscopy.

411

412 **Author Contributions**

413 The contributions to this research were as follows: FC planned the experimental design,
414 conducted the experiments, and wrote the manuscript. DK contributed significantly to the
415 experimental design and assisted in the preparation of the manuscript. FC and DC were
416 responsible for data analysis. EDK performed 3D plaque image analysis. AE, SL and PK jointly
417 conducted the analysis of 3D images of microglia. Figure preparation was a collaborative effort
418 involving FC, EDK and AE. AMR and CT provided key support in the execution of the
419 experiments, while DM and UW were integral to the animal experiments. LF brought key
420 expertise in the task of stitching 3D images. The project was overseen by JHL, PK and AA,
421 who not only supervised the entire work and contributed to the manuscript, but also played a
422 key role in securing financial support.

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429 **Materials and Methods**

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431 *APPS1 mice*

432 APPPS1 transgenic mice were used in the study, which co-express the Swedish mutation
433 K670M/N671L and PS1 mutation L166P under the control of the neuron-specific Thy-1
434 promoter on a C57BL/6 genetic background [32]. APPPS1 mice were habituated ahead of the
435 study to voluntarily drink condensed milk formulation from a pipette. The condensed milk used
436 in the study is commercially available (Migros) and contains milk, sugar, stabilizer E339. Body
437 weight was measured ahead of commencing the study to calculate the dose of netoglitazone
438 for each mouse and to calculate the total blood volume.

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440 *Animal treatments and tissue preparation*

441 All animal experiments were carried out in strict accordance with the Rules and Regulations
442 for the Protection of Animal Rights (Tierschutzgesetz and Tierschutzverordnung) of the Swiss
443 Bundesamt für Lebensmittelsicherheit und Veterinärwesen and were pre-emptively approved
444 by the Animal Welfare Committee of the Canton of Zürich (permit 040/2015). APPPS1 male
445 and female mice were treated daily orally with netoglitazone (Wren Therapeutics, Cambridge
446 UK) diluted in condensed milk (Migros, Switzerland) and PBS. The administered dosages
447 were either with 75mg/ml (high-dose) or 25mg/ml (low-dose). The treatment duration was for
448 either 90 or 180 days (short-term or long-term respectively). The dose was selected based on
449 previous work where pharmacokinetics showed that netoglitazone crossed the blood-brain
450 barrier after oral administration (15 mg/Kg) and could be detected in micro dialysate from
451 fraction 30-60 min post administration [82]. Control mice were treated with PBS (PBS and
452 condensed milk). The starting age of the treated mice were 56 ± 4 days (Fig. 2a). For whole-
453 brain analysis of A β plaques, the protocol was performed as previously described [60]. Briefly:
454 after treatments were completed, mice were deeply anaesthetized with ketamine and xylazine
455 and transcardially perfused first with ice cold PBS, followed by a hydrogel monomer mixture
456 of 4% acrylamide, 0.05% bisacrylamide, and 1% paraformaldehyde. Brains were harvested,
457 post incubated in hydrogel mixture overnight and further cleared. For whole-hemisphere
458 analysis of microglia, 2D immunofluorescence (IF), 2D immunohistochemistry (IHC), and RNA
459 sequencing (RNAseq) analysis: mice were deeply anaesthetized with ketamine and xylazine
460 and transcardially perfused first with ice cold PBS, followed by 4% paraformaldehyde. Brains
461 were harvested, and the hemispheres were separated. Left hemispheres were further
462 incubated in the paraformaldehyde solution for 24 hours, then moved to 30% sucrose in PBS
463 for two days at 4 °C and finally they were embedded in paraffin to be further used for whole-

464 hemisphere analysis of microglia, IF, and IHC. Right hemispheres were snap-frozen right after
465 harvesting and stored at -80 °C.

466
467 *Behavioral studies*

468 Groups of 10 APPPS1 [32] mice and wild-type (WT) mice treated for 180 days with high-dose
469 of netoglitazone (10 mice per group) and respective controls (PBS) were tested approximately
470 3-4 days prior perfusion for the following behavioral paradigms:

471 *Light/dark box (LDB) test*

472 The LDB test was used to measure anxiety-like behavior in mice [83]. The LDB consists of
473 four identical two-way shuttle boxes (30 x 30 x 24 cm; Multi Conditioning System, TSE
474 Systems GmbH, Bad-Homburg, Germany). The boxes are each separated by dark plexiglass
475 walls, which are interconnected by an opening (3.5 × 10 cm) in the partition wall, thus allowing
476 the animal to freely traverse from one compartment to the other. This wall divides the
477 compartment into a dark (1 lux) and a brightly illuminated (100 lux) compartment. Mice were
478 individually placed in the center of the dark compartment and were allowed to move freely for
479 10 min. The distance moved in the light compartment was assessed as an index of innate
480 anxiety in mice [84] (Figure 1C).

481 *Spatial recognition memory*

482 Spatial recognition memory is evaluated by a spatial novelty preference task in the Y-maze
483 [85]. The apparatus was made of transparent Plexiglas and consists of three identical arms
484 (50 × 9 cm; length × width) surrounded by 10-cm high transparent Plexiglas walls. The three
485 arms radiated from a central triangle (8 cm on each side) and were spaced 120° from each
486 other. Access to each arm from the central area can be blocked by a removable opaque barrier
487 wall. The maze was elevated 90 cm above the floor and positioned in a well-lit room enriched
488 with distal spatial cues. For each retention interval to be tested (see below), the experiment
489 was performed in a different room with a distinct set of extra-maze cues surrounding the Y-
490 maze, to avoid confounds by familiar visual cues. A digital camera was mounted above the Y-
491 maze apparatus. Images were captured at a rate of 5 Hz and transmitted to a PC running the
492 EthoVision tracking system (Noldus Information Technology), calculating the time spent and
493 distance moved in the three arms and center zone of the Y-maze. The test of spatial
494 recognition memory in the Y-maze consisted of two phases, called the sample and choice
495 phases. The allocation of arms (start, familiar and novel arm) to a specific spatial location is
496 counterbalanced across the subjects.

497 • Sample phase: The animals were allowed to explore two arms (referred to as 'start arm' and
498 'familiar arm'). Access to the remaining arm ('novel arm') was blocked by a barrier wall door.

499 To begin a trial, the animal was introduced at the end of the start arm and allowed to freely
500 explore both the start and the familiar arms for 5 min. The animals were then removed and
501 kept in a holding cage during the specific retention intervals (see below) prior to the choice
502 phase. The barrier door was removed and the floor was cleaned to avoid olfactory cues.

503 • Choice phase: Following a specific retention interval (see below), the test animal was
504 introduced to the maze again. During the choice phase, the barrier wall was removed so that
505 the animals could freely explore all arms of the maze for 5 min. The subject was then removed
506 from the maze and returned to the home cage. For each trial, the time spent in each of the
507 three arms was recorded. The relative time spent in the novel arm during the choice phase
508 was calculated by the formula $([\text{time spent in the novel arm}/[\text{time spent in all arms}]] \times 100$ and
509 used as the index for spatial novelty preference. In addition, total distance moved on the entire
510 maze was recorded and analyzed in order to assess general locomotor activity. To manipulate
511 the retention demand in the temporal domain, the interval between the two phases (i.e. sample
512 and choice phases) of the Y-maze test was varied. First, a minimal interval of 1 min was used.
513 The interval between the two phases was then increased to 2h (Supplementary Figure 1A,
514 1B).

515 *Open field exploration test*

516 The open field paradigm was used to study of basal locomotor activity [86]. The open field
517 exploration test was conducted in four identical square arenas (40×40×35 cm high) made of
518 opaque acryl glass. They were located in a testing room under diffused lighting (approximately
519 25 lx as measured in the center of the arenas). A digital camera was mounted directly above
520 the four arenas. Images were captured at a rate of 5 Hz and transmitted to a PC running the
521 Ethovision (Noldus, The Netherlands) tracking system. For measuring basal locomotor
522 activity, the animals were gently placed in the center of the arena and allowed to explore for
523 10 min. Distance moved in the entire arena was assessed to index locomotor activity
524 (Supplementary Figure 1C).

525 *Temporal order memory test*

526 A temporal order memory test was used as a test for prefrontal cortex-dependent short-term
527 memory. The mouse was first subjected to a training trial, where it was placed in an open field
528 (square arena 40×40×35 cm high) with two copies of a novel object and allowed to explore
529 them for 10 min. After the 10 min exploration, the mouse was placed back into a waiting cage.
530 After a delay of 60 min, the mouse received a second training trial identical to the first, except
531 that two copies of a new novel object will be present. Again, after the second training trial the
532 mouse was placed back into the waiting cage. After a further delay of either 2 h or no delay,
533 the mouse received a test trial identical to the training trials, except that one copy of the object

534 from trial 1 (the old familiar object) and one copy of the object from trial 2 (the recent familiar
535 object) were presented. For each animal, a temporal order memory index was calculated by
536 the formula: $([\text{time spent with phase 1 object}] / [\text{time spent with phase 1 object} + \text{time spent}$
537 $\text{with phase 2 object}]) * 100$. The temporal order memory index was used to compare the
538 animals' capacity to discriminate the relative regency of stimuli [87], with values > 50 signifying
539 a capacity to discriminate between the temporally more remote object presented in sample
540 phase 1 and the temporally more recent object presented in sample phase 2. In addition, the
541 relative amount of time exploring the objects in sample phases 1 and 2 of the test were
542 analyzed to measure object exploration per se (Figure 2E).

543 *Contextual Fear Conditioning*

544 Contextual fear conditioning and extinction were conducted using 4 identical multi-conditioning
545 chambers (Multi Conditioning System, TSE Systems, Bad Homburg, Germany), in which the
546 animals were confined to a rectangular enclosure (30 [length] × 30 [width] × 36 [height] cm)
547 made of black acrylic glass. The chambers were equivalently illuminated by a red house light
548 (30 lux) and were equipped with a grid floor made of 29 stainless rods (4 mm in diameter and
549 10 mm apart; inter-rod center to inter-rod center), through which a scrambled electric shock
550 could be delivered. Each chamber was surrounded by 3 infrared light-beam sensor systems,
551 with sensors spaced 14 mm apart, allowing movement detection in 3 dimensions. The
552 contextual fear conditioning and extinction test followed protocols established before [33, 88]
553 and consistent of 3 phases, which were each separated 24h apart (see below). During all three
554 phases, the red house light was on at all times. Conditioned fear was expressed as freezing
555 behavior, which was quantified automatically by program-guided algorithms as time of
556 immobility. Habituation and conditioning phase: The animals were placed in the designated
557 test chamber and were allowed to freely explore the chamber for 3 min. This served to
558 habituate the animals to the chamber. Conditioning commenced immediately at the end of the
559 habituation period without the animals being removed from the chambers. For conditioning,
560 the animals were exposed to 3 conditioning trials, whereby each conditioning trial began with
561 the delivery of a 1 second foot-shock set at 0.3 mA and was followed by a 90s rest period.
562 The animals were removed from the chambers and were placed back in their home cages
563 immediately after the last trial. Fear expression phase: The fear expression phase took place
564 24h and 48h after conditioning when the animals were returned to the same chambers in the
565 absence of any discrete stimulus other than the context. To assess conditioned fear towards
566 to the context, percent time freezing was measured for a period of 6 min. The animals were
567 then removed from the boxes and placed back to their home cages (Figure 2C).

568

569 *Tissue clearing and staining of A β plaques with focused electrophoretic tissue*

570 For whole-brain analysis of A β plaques, brains were cleared with focused electrophoretic
571 tissue clearing (FEC) in accordance to [60]. Briefly: Brains were placed in a custom-built
572 chamber in 8% clearing solution (8% w/w sodium dodecyl sulphate in 200 mM boric acid, pH
573 8.5) and cleared for approximately 16h at 130 mA current-clamped and at a voltage limit of
574 60V, at 39.5 °C. Transparency was assessed by visual inspection. Immunofluorescence
575 staining of A β plaques was performed in accordance to the protocol described in [60]. Briefly:
576 amyloid plaques were stained with a combination of luminescent conjugated polythiophenes
577 (LCPs), heptamer-formyl thiophene acetic acid (hFTAA), and quadro-formyl thiophene acetic
578 acid (qFTAA). The combination of these dyes was used for the discrimination of neuritic
579 plaques at different maturation states [89]. After staining brains were refractive index (RI) -
580 matched to 1.46 with a modified version of the refractive index matching solution [90] by
581 including triethanolamine [60] (Supplementary Figure 3).

582

583 *Whole-brain imaging of A β plaques*

584 Whole brain images were recorded with a custom-made selective plane illumination
585 microscope (www.mesospim.org) [36]. SPIM imaging was done after clearing and refractive
586 index matching as previously described in [60]. Briefly: the laser/filter combinations for
587 mesoSPIM imaging were as follows: for qFTAA at 488 nm excitation, a 498 - 520 nm
588 bandpass filter (BrightLine 509/22 HC, Semrock / AHF) was used as the emission filter; for
589 hFTAA at 488 nm excitation, a 565 - 605 nm bandpass filter (585/40 BrightLine HC , Semrock
590 / AHF) was used. Transparent whole-brains were imaged at a voxel size of 3.26 \times 3.26 \times 3
591 μm^3 (X \times Y \times Z). For scanning a whole brain, 16 tiles per channel were imaged (8 tiles per
592 brain hemisphere). After the acquisition of one hemisphere, the sample was rotated and the
593 other hemisphere was then acquired. The entire process was followed by stitching [91]
594 (Supplementary Figure 3).

595

596 *Tissue clearing and whole-hemisphere staining of microglia with DISCO*

597 Mouse hemispheres were stained for microglia using a modified version of the iDISCO
598 protocol [39]. Deparaffination was performed using a custom-developed protocol as part of
599 the aDISCO protocol (unpublished). Paraffin-embedded mouse hemispheres were melted for
600 1 hour at 60°C, followed by incubation in xylene for 1 hour at 37°C and 65 rpm and for 1 hour
601 at room temperature (RT) and 40 rpm. Rehydration was performed by serial incubations of
602 100%, 95%, 90%, 80%, 70%, 50%, and 25% ethanol (EtOH) in ddH₂O, followed by incubation

603 in PBS overnight at RT and 40 rpm. Samples were again dehydrated in serial incubations of
604 20%, 40%, 60%, 80% methanol (MeOH) in ddH₂O, followed by 2 times 100% MeOH, each for
605 1 hour at RT and 40 rpm. Pre-clearing was performed in 33% MeOH in dichloromethane
606 (DCM) overnight at RT and 40 rpm. After 2 times washing in 100% MeOH each for 1 hour at
607 RT and then 4°C at 40 rpm, bleaching was performed in 5% hydrogen peroxide in MeOH for
608 20 hours at 4°C and 40 rpm. Samples were rehydrated in serial incubations of 80%, 60%,
609 40%, and 20% MeOH in in ddH₂O, followed by PBS, each for 1 hour at RT and 40 rpm.
610 Permeabilization was performed by incubating the mouse hemispheres 2 times in 0.2%
611 TritonX-100 in PBS each for 1 hour at RT and 40 rpm, followed by incubation in 0.2% TritonX-
612 100 + 10% dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) + 2.3% glycine + 0.1% sodium azide (NaN₃) in PBS
613 for 5 days at 37°C and 65 rpm. Blocking was performed in 0.2% Tween-20 + 0.1% heparin
614 (10 mg/ml) + 5% DMSO + 6% donkey serum in PBS for 2 days at 37°C and 65 rpm. Samples
615 were stained gradually with primary polyclonal rabbit-anti-Iba1 antibody (Wako, 019-19741)
616 1:400, followed by secondary polyclonal 647-conjugated donkey-anti-rabbit antibody
617 (ThermoFisher, A-31573) in 0.2% Tween-20 + 0.1% heparin + 5% DMSO + 0.1% NaN₃ in
618 PBS (staining buffer) in a total volume of 1.5 ml per sample every week for 2 weeks at 37°C
619 and 65 rpm. Washing steps were performed in staining buffer 5 times each for 1 hour, and
620 then for 1-2 days at RT and 40 rpm. Clearing was started by dehydrating the samples in serial
621 MeOH incubations as described above. Delipidation was performed in 33% MeOH in DCM
622 overnight at RT and 40 rpm, followed by 2 times 100% DCM each for 20 minutes at RT and
623 40 rpm. Refractive index (RI) matching was achieved in dibenzyl ether (DBE, RI = 1.56) for 4
624 hours at RT. 3D stacks of cleared mouse hemispheres were acquired using the mesoSPIM
625 light-sheet microscope [36] (www.mesospim.org) at 2X zoom with a field of view of 1.3 cm and
626 isotropic resolution of 3 μm/voxel. To image the microglia a 640nm laser and a F76 647SG
627 long pass filter were used. Imaged tiles were stitched together [91] and raw data were post-
628 processed using Fiji (Image J, 1.8.0_172 64 bit) and Imaris (Oxford Instruments, 9.8.0)
629 (Supplementary Figure 3).

630

631 *2D immunofluorescence staining of Aβ plaques with antibody*

632 Slices from formalin fixed and paraffin embedded brain tissue from 180 day-treated APPPS1
633 mice (n=3) were stained for Aβ plaques. Slices were stained with mouse anti-human Aβ₁₋₁₆
634 antibody (6E10, Biolegend SIG-39320, 1:200) after antigen retrieval with 10% formic acid.
635 Slices were blocked with M.O.M. Kit (BMK-2202) and the primary antibody was detected with
636 Alexa-488 conjugated goat anti-mouse IgG (Invitrogen A-11005, 1:1000 dilution) followed by
637 diamidino-phenylindole (DAPI) staining. Slices were imaged with a Leica SP5 confocal
638 microscope. Nuclei and plaques were imaged with a 10X/0.25 (numerical aperture 0.4). NA

639 dry objective, using the following settings: 405 nm excitation for DAPI (nuclei) and 488nm
640 excitation for amyloid. The dynamic range of images was adjusted consistently across images.
641 Three different cortical regions and one thalamic region were selected per slice (2 slices per
642 sample). Pixels representing the region of interest were classified and counted as plaques
643 (6E10-Alexa488 positive) or background (6E10-Alexa488 negative) with a manually trained
644 (trained on ten images) pixel classifier in ILASTIK [38], and ImageJ. Hypothesis testing was
645 done with a 2-tailed T-test (Supplementary Figure 4B).

646

647 *2D immunohistochemistry staining of A β plaques with antibody*

648 Slices from formalin fixed and paraffin embedded brain tissue from 180 day-treated APPPS1
649 mice (n=3) were stained for A β plaques. 6- μ m-thick paraffin sections (3 sections per mouse)
650 were deparaffinized through a decreasing alcohol series. Slices were stained with Slices were
651 stained with mouse anti-human A β ₁₋₁₆ antibody (6E10, Biolegend SIG-39320, 1:200) and
652 detected using an IVIEW DAB Detection Kit (Ventana). Sections were imaged using a Zeiss
653 Axiophot light microscope. For the quantification of plaque staining in the whole section, pixels
654 were classified and counted as plaques (A β positive) or background (A β negative) with a
655 manually trained (trained on five images) pixel classifier in ILASTIK [92], and ImageJ.
656 Hypothesis testing was done with a 2-tailed T-test (Supplementary Figure 4A).

657

658 *Drug distribution measurements in plasma*

659 7 days and 28 days post dosing, serial blood samples (~50 μ L) were taken from the tail vein of
660 individual animals and delivered into labelled Safe-lock Eppendorf 1.5 mL clear (e.g. T9661
661 Sigma Aldrich) containing Na-heparin as the anticoagulant (1000iU, 2 μ L per vial). The
662 samples was held on wet ice for a maximum of 30 minutes while sampling of all the animals
663 in the cohort was completed. The blood samples were centrifuged for plasma (4°C, 2000-
664 3000g for 8 min) and 25 μ L of the resulting plasma were analyzed. Drug concentration in
665 plasma was calculated by Parmidex, London, UK (Figure 1B).

666

667 *Computational and statistical analysis for whole-brain A β quantification*

668 The following computations were performed using custom scripts written in Python and R [93]
669 as well as existing third-party libraries as previously described[60]. Briefly, the 2-channel (498–
670 520 nm and 565-605 nm) sub-stacks for each brain hemisphere were first stitched together
671 with TeraStitcher [91]. The result was down sampled from the acquired resolution (3.26 μ m
672 lateral, 3 μ m depth) to an isotropic 25 μ m resolution and then registered to the Allen Brain

673 Atlas 25 μm average anatomical template atlas [40]. The 565-605 nm channel at its original
674 resolution was used to determine the locations of aggregates of amyloid- β stained with qFTAA
675 and hFTAA. A random forest classifier was used to classify each voxel as either “belonging to
676 a plaque” or “background” using the open-source Ilastik framework [92] as described in [60].
677 After down-sampling each aggregate center to 25- μm resolution and applying the optimized
678 registration transformation, the number of aggregates were counted at each voxel in this atlas
679 space and smoothed heatmaps were generated by placing a spherical ROI with 15-voxel
680 diameter (= 375 μm) at each voxel and summing the plaque counts within the ROI, as
681 described in [60] (Supplementary Figure 3A, 3B).

682 Voxel-level statistics across treated and control brains involved running a two-sided t-test at
683 each heatmap voxel across the two groups. The three-dimensional statistical maps were
684 adjusted using the threshold-free cluster enhancement method [94]. These adjusted p-value
685 maps were then binarized with a threshold of 0.05 for subsequent analysis or visualization.
686 The transformed locations of each plaque were further grouped into 52 different anatomically
687 segmented regions in the Allen Reference Atlas (25) for further statistical analysis between
688 longitudinal groups. These anatomical regions were masked to only include voxels that
689 demonstrated a statistically significant difference ($p < 0.05$).

690

691 *Computational and statistical analysis for whole-hemisphere microglia quantification*

692 The 640 nm channel in its original resolution was used to determine the spatial density of
693 microglia and all the substacks for each brain hemisphere were first stitched together with
694 Terastitcher [91]. Advanced filtering techniques implemented in Python and C were used
695 within a custom pipeline, available on github ([https://github.com/aecon/3D-microglia-](https://github.com/aecon/3D-microglia-netoglitazone)
696 [netoglitazone](https://github.com/aecon/3D-microglia-netoglitazone)), aimed at high-speed processing of 3D half-brain mouse datasets. The pipeline
697 consists of three main steps: (i) image restoration, (ii) voxel-based microglia detection, and
698 (iii) regional microglia-density quantification. First, image restoration was performed to
699 alleviate low frequency background (autofluorescence) undulations, and remove high
700 frequency noise at the voxel level introduced during the digitization of the image via the
701 microscope camera [95]. Specifically, background intensity is modelled via Gaussian
702 smoothing of the raw data. The variance is set to 50 voxels, such that it is larger than the
703 typical foreground (microglia) radius, but smaller than the typical radius of background regions
704 with high autofluorescence. The background undulations are removed by dividing the raw data
705 with the smoothed data [96], yielding the normalized data. Lastly, digitization noise is
706 suppressed via a Gaussian smoothing of the normalized image with a small variance of 1
707 voxel, modelling the intervoxel noise. Microglia detection was performed by applying a

708 minimum threshold on the normalized intensity data. The threshold was set to 1.8 for all
709 samples, chosen such that large and bright microglia are detected, while at the same time
710 noise and regions of high tissue autofluorescence are excluded. This leads to the binarized
711 data where each pixel is classified as background or foreground. Connected foreground voxels
712 are identified as single microglia cells, and thresholds on the minimum possible microglia
713 volume and minimum maximum microglia intensity are applied to eliminate smaller and/or
714 dimmer artifacts. The segmentation results for all 9 samples were validated by a domain
715 expert, through a visual inspection of the detected microglia overlaid on the raw data
716 (Supplementary Figure 5).

717 Spatial distribution of microglia volume was then estimated by mapping the detected microglia
718 on the Allen Reference Atlas. This step was achieved using elastix [97] where
719 the autofluorescence from the plaque channel (565-605 nm) was first down-sampled to the
720 atlas resolution (25 μm per voxel side) and then used to spatially transform
721 the autofluorescence data such that they match the atlas geometry. This process gave an
722 optimized registration transformation per sample. The optimized transformation was then
723 applied on the detected microglia voxels, after down-sampling to the atlas resolution.
724 Assuming that the density is constant over all selected microglia voxels, the total microglia
725 volume per atlas voxel was computed by counting the number of microglia voxels mapped
726 onto each atlas voxel. The quantification of microglia distribution was performed using density
727 plots, depicting the volume of detected microglia inside a cubic pixel with the atlas
728 resolution. Similar to the plaque quantification, smoothed heatmaps were generated by
729 placing a spherical ROI with 15-voxel diameter and taking a weighted sum of the microglia
730 volume within the ROI. Coronal sections of the volume distribution for every sample, were
731 overlaid on the respective slices of the Allen Brain Atlas (Fig. 5a). The average microglia
732 volume distribution per group was computed by taking the mean over the samples belonging
733 to each group (Fig. 5b). Using the 134 different anatomically segmented regions of the Allen
734 Reference Atlas, the anatomical regions of the detected microglia were identified, and the total
735 volume in six brain regions was computed: brain stem, hippocampus, hypothalamus, cortex,
736 thalamus, cerebellum. The group-wise average microglia volume and corresponding standard
737 deviation per brain region were then computed. To measure the degree of spatial
738 colocalization between microglia cell count change and plaque count change following long-
739 term treatments of either low or high dose drug, thresholded voxel level statistical maps ($p <$
740 0.05 , corrected) for each group were first generated in the Allen Coordinate Space. To
741 compare two statistical maps from different groups, we calculate the number of overlapping
742 voxels between the significantly increasing, or decreasing, parts of the first map with the
743 significantly increasing, or decreasing, parts of another map. This results in four distinct

744 comparisons, and a colocalization matrix as depicted in Figure 4B. This analysis was
745 performed for comparing the changes in microglia cell count with plaque changes in the low
746 dose (long-term) treatment group, and separately for comparing the changes in microglia cell
747 count with plaque changes in the high dose (long-term) treatment group.

748

749 *RNA sequencing*

750 Group of treated and controls APPPS1 mice (7 high-dose, low-dose and 7 PBS-treated mice)
751 were analyzed for transcriptomic changes. Snap-frozen hemispheres were sectioned in slices
752 of 10 μ m, and total RNA was extracted by following a standard RNA extraction protocol (TRIzol
753 Reagent Ref. 15596026). The RNA quality and quantity were assessed using a
754 spectrophotometer, and only high-quality RNA samples were used for subsequent RNA-seq
755 library preparation. The RNA-seq libraries were prepared using a library preparation kit
756 compatible with the sequencing platform (Nova Seq Illumina Library) following the
757 manufacturer's instructions. Subsequently, the libraries were sequenced on a high-throughput
758 sequencing instrument, generating millions of reads per sample.

759 Post-processed DEGs were visualized with volcano plot showing statistical significance (P-
760 value) versus magnitude of change (fold change). Statistical threshold has been applied prior
761 data visualization (absolute log₂ fold change > 0.5 and pvalue < 0.005). Customized script
762 was used to generate the related plot by using R and RStudio platform. For data wrangling,
763 the tidyverse, tidyr and dyplr R packages have been used, while for data visualization ggplot2
764 and ggpubr packages were used. Differential downregulated genes are shown in green,
765 whereas upregulated genes in magenta.

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778

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806 **Figures and Figure legends**

807

808 **Figure 1: 180 days of treatment with netoglitzazone induces anxiolytic-like effects, alters**
 809 **fear memory and restores deficit in temporal order memory in AD mice.** (A) APPPS1
 810 mice were treated daily with either a high dose (75 mg/ml) or a low dose (15 mg/ml) of
 811 netoglitzazone or appropriate control (PBS). Treatment started at 2 months of age and
 812 continued for either three or six months. Mice were perfused and brains were further analyzed
 813 at either five or eight months of age. Behavioral studies and RNAseq analysis were performed
 814 only on mice treated for 180 days with a high dose of netoglitzazone. (B) Blood was withdrawn
 815 from mice of the long-term treatment cohort seven and twenty-eight days after the start of the
 816 treatment. Drug concentration was measured in the plasma. Plasma drug concentration
 817 increased in line with time in both dosing cohorts. (C) Behavioral tests: Drug treatment induced
 818 anxiolytic-like effects in Tg animals, as indexed by an increased distance moved in the light
 819 compartment when compared to untreated Tg animals, as well as to wild type (WT) animals,
 820 without affecting general maze exploration. (D) Contextual fear memory: In male mice, long-
 821 term drug treatment enhanced expression of contextual fear independent of the genotype after
 822 24h. After 48h, transgenic (Tg) mice displayed a reduction in fear memory, with a treatment-

823 dependent increase, independent of genotype. (E) Tg animals displayed a deficit in temporal
824 order memory, which was restored to control levels by the drug treatment. This was not
825 confounded by changes in the preference towards one of the distinct sets of objects.

826

832 decrease in plaque count, and the cyan scale represents an increase. The reference atlas is
833 depicted in grey. The maps provide a comprehensive summary of treated and control samples
834 within each cohort, with 6-8 samples per group. Additionally, the plots on the right side display
835 the average plaque count across the cohorts. The figure highlights the regiospecific efficacy
836 unique to each treatment modality: (A) Short-treatment with a low dose of netoglitazone shows
837 a patchy effect in reducing plaque count, primarily observed in the olfactory, striatal, and
838 thalamic areas. (B) Long-term-treatment with a low dose of netoglitazone also exhibits a
839 patchy effect in decreasing plaque count. This effect is mainly observed in the olfactory,
840 hindbrain, and visual areas. Notably, there is a patchy increase in plaque count observed in
841 the hippocampal, cortical, striatal, and midbrain areas. (C) Short-treatment with a high dose
842 of netoglitazone reveals a significant reduction in plaque count, particularly in the hindbrain,
843 midbrain, striatum, and olfactory areas. (D) Long-term treatment with a high dose of
844 netoglitazone demonstrates a considerable decrease in plaque count, especially in the
845 olfactory, striatum, pallidum, hindbrain, and midbrain regions.

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848

849 **Figure 3: Voxel-based whole-brain analysis shows regional and dose-dependent effects**
 850 **of netoglitazone in decreasing plaque mean size.** The figure presents a series of maps and
 851 plots illustrating the effects of different treatments on plaque size. Each map represents a 3-

852 dimensional view of statistically affected voxels ($p < 0.05$), where the red scale indicates a
853 decrease in plaque size, and the cyan scale represents an increase. The reference atlas is
854 depicted in grey. The maps provide a comprehensive summary of treated and control samples
855 within each cohort, with 6-8 samples per group. Additionally, the plots on the right side display
856 the average plaque count across the cohorts. The figure highlights the regiospecific efficacy
857 unique to each treatment modality: (A) Short-treatment with a low dose of netoglitazone
858 displays a notable patchy effect in reducing plaque size, primarily observed in the olfactory,
859 hippocampal, striatal, thalamic, and midbrain areas. (B) Long-term-treatment with a low dose
860 of netoglitazone demonstrates a patchy effect primarily in increasing plaque size, mainly
861 observed in the optical cortex, visual area, hippocampus, striatum, and hindbrain. However,
862 there is only a minimal effect on decreasing plaque size. (C) Short-treatment with a high dose
863 of netoglitazone reveals a significant reduction in plaque size, especially observed in the
864 hippocampus, striatum, thalamus, hypothalamus, midbrain, and hindbrain. Additionally, there
865 is an increase in plaque size mainly observed in the olfactory, hippocampal, cortical, and
866 striatal areas. (D) Long-term treatment with a high dose of netoglitazone displays a decrease
867 in plaque size, particularly observed in the orbital cortex, olfactory area, hippocampus,
868 thalamus, hypothalamus, midbrain, and hindbrain regions.

869

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871

872 **Figure 4: Voxel-based whole-hemisphere analysis shows regional and dose-dependent**
 873 **decrease of microglia.** (A) Each 3-dimensional map of statistically affected voxels ($p < 0.05$,
 874 with the red scale, representing the significance in decrease of microglia, and the cyan scale,
 875 representing the increase in microglia; reference atlas is grey) summarizes all the treated and
 876 control samples within a cohort (3 samples per group). These maps illustrate that the
 877 effectiveness of reducing microglia is specific to particular regions and varies based on the
 878 dosage of the treatment. When netoglitazone is administered in low doses over long-term
 879 treatment, it only has a limited impact on reducing the overall volume of microglia. However,
 880 when high doses of netoglitazone are administered for long-term, it produces a significant and
 881 scattered effect, leading to a noticeable reduction in microglia volume in cortical and
 882 hippocampal regions. (B) Colocalizing a microglia statistical map with an A β plaque statistical
 883 maps allows for calculations of the number of overlapping voxels with statistically significant
 884 increase or decrease across the two maps. For the late low dose treatment, an increase in A β
 885 plaque count was colocalized with decreased microglia. For the late high dose treatment, the
 886 decrease in A β plaque count was also colocalized with decreased microglia.

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890 **Figure 5: Gene expression changes are revealed by RNAseq upon long-term treatment**

891 **with netoglitazone.** (A) Volcano plots depicting the gene regulation effects of long-term

892 treatment with netoglitazone at different doses. The plots include genes that exhibit significant

893 regulation, determined using thresholds of $abs|\log_2FC| > 0.5$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.005$. The

894 volcano plot for long-term treatment with a low dose of netoglitazone illustrates the significantly

895 regulated genes. Upregulated genes are represented in magenta, while downregulated genes

896 are shown in green. In comparison to the PBS group, animals treated with a low dose of

897 netoglitazone display a notable number of both downregulated and upregulated differentially

898 expressed genes (DEGs). (B) The volcano plot for long-term treatment with a high dose of

899 netoglitazone depicts the significantly regulated genes. Similar to the previous plot,

900 upregulated genes are indicated in magenta, while downregulated genes are displayed in

901 green. However, in contrast to the low dose treatment, animals treated with a high dose of

902 netoglitazone exhibit a minimal number of both downregulated and upregulated DEGs

903 compared to the PBS group.

904

905 **References**

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Figure 1

Figure 1

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Overlap in significant voxels

Figure 4

Figure 4

Figure 5

Figure 5